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Liver resection in elderly patients with extensive CRLM: are we offering the right treatment? A propensity score matched analysis

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Abstract:	<p>Background: Data on the management of elderly patients with extensive colorectal liver metastases (CRLM) are scarce and conflicting. This study assesses differences in management and long-term oncological outcomes between older and younger patients with CRLM and a high Tumour Burden Score (TBS).</p> <p>Methods: International multicentre retrospective study on patients with CRLM and a category 3 TBS, submitted to liver resection. Patients were divided into two groups according to their age (younger and older than 75) and were compared using propensity score matching (PSM) analysis and multivariable regression models. Differences in management and oncological outcomes including recurrence-free survival (RFS) and overall survival (OS) were assessed</p>

	<p>Results: The study included 386 patients, median follow-up was 48 months. The unmatched comparison revealed a higher ASA score ($p=0.035$), less synchronous CRLM (47% vs 68%, $p=0.003$), a lower median number of lesions (1 vs 3, $p=0.004$) and less perioperative chemotherapy (CTx) (66% vs 88%, $p<0.001$) in the elderly group. Despite the absence of CTx being an independent predictor of decreased RFS and OS (HR 0.760, $p=0.044$ and HR 0.719, $p=0.049$, respectively), the elderly group still received less CTx (OR 0.317, $p=0.001$) than the younger group. After PSM ($n=100$ patients), the two groups were comparable, however, CTx administration was still significantly lower in the elderly group. Conclusion: Liver resection should be considered in patients aged 75 and older, even if they present with extensive liver disease. Despite CTx being associated with improved oncological outcomes, a large percentage of elderly patients with CRLM are undertreated.</p>
<p>Response to Reviewers:</p>	<p>All reviewers comments have been responded in the attached File: Reviewers response</p>

Cover Letter for Manuscript Submission

Dr. Marcello Di Martino, M.D. Ph. D.

Dear Editor-in-Chief,

We are writing to submit our manuscript entitled “*Liver resection in elderly patients with extensive CRLM: are we offering the right treatment? A propensity score matched analysis*” We would like to have the manuscript considered for publication in ESJO as *Original Article*.

This article is a multicentric international study assessing the controversy regarding the role of liver resection (LR) and perioperative chemotherapy (CTx) in elderly patients with resectable colorectal liver metastases (CRLM). More specifically, it focuses on the role of LR and CTx in those patients with extensive CRLM, such as those with a Tumour Burden Score (TBS) of 3 (the highest category).

Despite the increasing incidence of elderly patients diagnosed with CRLM, those subjects are often undertreated, and dedicated management protocols are lacking. Studies which take into consideration the subgroup of elderly patients stratified by the risk of disease recurrence are scarce. The current study is, to our knowledge, the first to describe the actual multidisciplinary management of those elderly patients with an increased risk of recurrence due to a high TBS.

This multicentric cohort included ten hospitals. After PSM analysis, LR was not associated with worse post-operative or oncological outcomes. However older patients received less perioperative CTx than younger ones. This finding is very important because, on multivariable analysis, perioperative chemotherapy administration was the only protective factor against early recurrence and decreased overall survival. Therefore, it appears that a large percentage of CRLM patients who could benefit from systemic therapy remain undertreated.

This manuscript describes a novel work and is not under consideration for publication/published by any other journal. All authors have approved the manuscript and this submission. The abstract has been accepted as oral presentation for the European-African Hepato-Pancreato-Biliary-Association Congress (E-AHPBA) 2021.

We therefore humbly feel that this report will serve as a useful and frequently-cited reference to EJSO readership and look forward to your kind consideration of our submission.

Kind Regards,
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Title of Manuscript:

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 "Liver resection in elderly patients with extensive CRLM: are we offering the right treatment? A propensity score matched analysis"

Name of corresponding author: Marcello Di Martino

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"All the authors have made a significant contribution to this manuscript, have seen and approved the final manuscript, and have agreed to its submission to the *EJSO*".

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(Please note that this form must be signed by ALL authors)

Changes in the manuscript based on reviewers' suggestions will be highlighted using red bold characters.

Reviewer #1:

- Firstly I congratulate the authors for their commitment on putting together such a collaborative team and for the decision to address the topic of treatment of elderly patients with colorectal liver metastases, an issue particularly in need of more accurate data to guide its management.
 - **We would like to thank the reviewer for these kind words. We strongly agree with the need of more accurate data to address an important topic such the treatment of CRLM in elderly patients.**

- That said, there are some points that need a closer attention before considering the manuscript for publication in EJSO:
- The concept of right or wrong is debatable in many clinical settings, including this one. This is specially worth of attention considering the clinical meaningful of the 5-year OS rate of 25% for patients with a category 3 TBS, regardless the treatment adopted. Maybe the title could be edicted to something as "offering an adequate treatment?"
 - **Thank you for the comment. We indeed agree with the reviewer on this point. Therefore, we changed the title of the manuscript as follow:**
 - *Page 1. Liver resection in elderly patients with extensive CRLM: are we offering an adequate treatment? A propensity score matched analysis*

- In the study design session on materials and methods the need of being treated on specialist liver surgery units is stated, although we know many patients are not. Please comment on the risk of selection bias with this approach. What about having an indiscriminate analysis of treatment of this subset of patients in general?
 - **Thank you for rising this interesting point. Based on the reviewer comment we changed the discussion of the study limitation as follow:**

- *Page 9: Furthermore, the decisions on the management of each patient were taken by local multidisciplinary teams, and the reasons to treat or not to treat a patient were not recorded for the analysis. Included patients were all treated in specialized liver surgery units. **This is not the standard of care for many patients which are treated in non-specialized hospitals. Therefore, the results of the current study could be subject to selection bias.***

- Which definition of elderly the authors implemented? How had they defined the 75-Years threshold? Would be the results any different if they had set the bar at 65 or 70?

- **This is another interesting point raised by the reviewer. We did not want to enter in a detailed discussion of the definition of “elderly” person because we thought that it was beyond the scope of this study. Therefore, we chose an arbitrary definition based on previous publications (number 1 and 29 in the bibliography). We should consider that the definition of “elderly” person is considered arbitrary in its own nature by many authors (Reviewing the definition of “elderly”. Orimo et al. Geriatrics and gerontology international. 2006). However, we agree with the reviewer that an explication of the age cut-off used in the manuscript is necessary. Based on this consideration we added the following paragraph in the Method section:**

- *Page 4: The reason for choosing the >75 years old cut-off was based on previous publications showing the results of CRLM resection in the U.S. population (29). Furthermore, 75 years of age represents the middle point between “older people” (>65 years old) and “very old people” (>85 years of age) following the definition of the Statistical Office of the European Union (1).*

- **We also discussed the decision of using this cut-off in the Discussion of the article as follow:**

- *Page 9: We also acknowledge that the definition of elderly patient used in this study is somewhat arbitrary, although based on previous publications (1, 29), and the use of a different age cut-off may have led to different results.*

- In table 2 we found that only 46% and 58% of patients from the elderly and younger groups respectively received an R0 resection. How can you explain that?
 - o **The reviewer is right. The R1 resection rate of the current series is higher than the one published by other authors (usually ranging from 10 to 25 % in unselected patients). The possible explanation for this finding is that this is a selected group of patients with a high TBS (category 3). Therefore, R1 resection rates can be higher due to the high burden of hepatic disease. Based on the reviewer comment with changed the first part of the Results section as follow:**
 - *Additionally, 252 patients (65.4%) presented with synchronous CRLM, with bilobar lesions in 147 (58.8%) cases. A major liver resection was required in 170 cases (44.2%) and 76 (21.1%) were associated with an ablative procedure. **The high R1 resection rate (43%) found in the current series was possibly related to the selection of patients with high tumour burden.** During the postoperative period, 67 patients (17.5%) presented with severe complications (\geq Clavien-Dindo IIIA), and there were 14 90 dayspostoperative deaths (3.7%).*

- in Table 3, the occurrence of postoperative major complications appears as a prognostic factor of OS but not for DFS. Please comment on that.
 - o **Thank you again for rising another important discussion point. In our opinion and based on works we previously published on this important topic (*Impact of type and severity of postoperative complications on long-term outcomes after colorectal liver metastases resection. J Surg Oncol. 2020 Aug;122(2):212-225. AND Impact of Postoperative Complications on Survival and Recurrence After Resection of Colorectal Liver Metastases: Systematic Review and Meta-analysis. Ann Surg. 2019 Dec;270(6):1018-1027.*) postoperative complications are an independent risk factor for CRLM recurrence. However, the current study was not powered to demonstrate the influence of complications on RFS. Therefore, I would speculate that the influence of complications on OS could reach statistical significance, but the influence on RFS could not, secondary to a type II error (small sample size). This is our personal opinion. Of course,**

we cannot prove that this result is not the consequence of the direct effect on mortality provoked by complications. We respectfully think that this topic is beyond the aim of the current work, and we fear that making a comment of this result in the paper would increase the complexity and cumbersome the discussion, without adding essential information on the main topic. However, if the reviewer and the editor think that it is necessary, we will be happy to add a paragraph to the discussion of the article to comment on this finding.

- Among the entire cohort 30.7% of patients with > 75 years were classified as ASA III or IV although in the PMS cohort this rate raised up to more than 60%. Even not being statistically significant when compared to patients younger than 75 Years-old, do you believe it would be clinically relevant in this scenario?
 - o **This is a very interesting observation. Actually, ASA II-IV patients were significantly more in the >75 group before PSM and that is factor which was corrected by the PSM. However, probably secondary to a reduced number of patients that could be matched between the two groups, the rate of ASAIII-IV patients in the <75 group raised more than expected. As highlighted by the reviewer, even if this difference was not statistically different, we cannot exclude that it could have influenced the long-term results. This is another limitation of this retrospective study: we could only use the ASA to assess the baseline status of the patients. Future prospective studies should definitively add other specific tools such as the Charlson or frailty evaluation scores. Based on this comment of the reviewer we further modified the discussion of the limitations of the study as follow:**
 - *Page 9: The current study has several limitations that should be taken into consideration. Its retrospective nature impeded the ability to properly assess the baseline status of included patients with dedicated tools, such as the Charlson comorbidity score or frailty evaluation tools (35). **The only score available to assess patients baseline status in this study was the ASA. As already mentioned, some results could be subject to type II errors and should be interpreted with caution.** Furthermore, the decisions on the management of each patient were taken by local*

multidisciplinary teams, and the reasons to treat or not to treat a patient were not recorded for the analysis. Included patients were all treated in specialized liver surgery units. This is not the standard of care for many European patients which are treated in non-specialized hospitals. Therefore, the results of the current study could be subject to selection bias. We also acknowledge that the definition of elderly patient used in this study is somewhat arbitrary, although based on previous publications (1, 29), and the use of a different age cut-off may have led to different results.

- If the survival outcomes are not any different, why authors believe the perioperative chemotherapy (or the lack of it) would have a impact on the observed results?

- o **Thank you for this consideration. We believe that chemotherapy administration would have an impact on survival based on multivariable analysis shown in Table 3. Chemotherapy administration is an independent protective factor for RFS and OS in our series of patients. This is an expected results in a selected cohort of patients with a high tumor burden such as the current. Furthermore, age >75 is the only independent risk factor for not receiving chemotherapy (Table 4). And this is the core of the problem which is depicted in our study: despite being possibly beneficial for better oncological outcomes, chemotherapy is not administered to elderly patients with high TBS.**

These findings, highlighted by the reviewer, have been commented in the discussion as follow

- *Page 8: In this multicentric cohort, including ten hospitals, older patients received less perioperative chemotherapy than younger ones, all recurrence risk factors being equalised by PSM. This finding is very important because, on multivariable analysis, perioperative chemotherapy administration was the only protective factor against early recurrence and decreased overall survival in this series of selected patients with a high TBS. Based on the current study, it appears that a large percentage of CRLM patients who could benefit from systemic therapy remain undertreated.*

- *Despite the difference in systemic treatment administration, elderly patients presented with similar RFS and OS to younger ones, confirming previous publications that have justified CRLM resection in this subgroup of patients (3, 5, 30). The added value of the current study is that it suggests that liver resection is oncologically justifiable even in those elderly patients with increased tumour burden.*
- **We understand that the reviewer comment is possibly driven by the fact that, after PSM, OS and RFS between the study groups were similar even if chemotherapy administration rate was lower in the >75yo group. That is completely true. We base our idea on the positive effect of chemotherapy on the results of the multivariable analysis. However, we agree that the only way to confirm this belief would be a prospective RCTs to evaluate chemotherapy administration in >75 years old patients with high TBS. Based on the comment above we added the following considerations to the discussion:**
 - *Page 8: Despite the difference in systemic treatment administration, elderly patients presented with similar RFS and OS to younger ones, confirming previous publications that have justified CRLM resection in this subgroup of patients (3, 5, 30). Prospective randomized trials, in our opinion, may be necessary to demonstrate the true benefit of chemotherapy administration in elderly patients. However, it is improbable that such trials will be feasible in short term.*
- Please see also the modification to the last paragraph of the discussion we did based on the second comment of Reviewer 2, which is in line with your current commentary.
 - *Page 9: Furthermore, it suggests that perioperative chemotherapy administration could be a protective factor against early recurrence and decreased overall survival in TBS>3 patients. However, a large percentage of elderly patients with CRLM and high tumor burden, who could possibly benefit from systemic therapy, were treated differently from younger ones. These findings should be considered as the basis for further prospective studies focused on the management of such patients.*

Reviewer #2:

- 1. Page 9 line 16-17 require clarification. 'During the postoperative period, 67 patients (17.5%) presented with severe complications (\geq Clavien-Dindo IIIA), and there were 14 90 dayspostoperative deaths (3.7%).'
 - o **Thank you for noticing this typo. We corrected the error and changed the paragraph as follows:**
 - *Page 5: During the postoperative period, 67 patients (17.5%) presented with severe complications (\geq Clavien-Dindo IIIA), and there were 14 postoperative deaths (3.7%).*

- 2. The concluding paragraph emphasizes the finding that 'perioperative chemotherapy administration being the only protective factor against early recurrence and decreased overall survival, a large percentage of patients with CRLM who could benefit from systemic therapy, were undertreated'. However, their results did not show a difference in either RFS or OS. This paragraph could be altered in order not to disregard this finding of the study.
 - o **Thank you for this comment that is in line with one of the considerations raised by reviewer 1. Based on this commentary we changed the last paragraph of the discussion as follow:**
 - *Page 9: Furthermore, it suggests that perioperative chemotherapy administration could be a protective factor against early recurrence and decreased overall survival in TBS 3 patients. However, a large percentage of elderly patients with high CRLM burden, who could possibly benefit from systemic therapy, were treated differently from younger ones. These findings should be considered as the basis for further prospective studies focused on the management of such patients.*

TITLE PAGE

TITLE

Liver resection in elderly patients with extensive CRLM: are we offering the right treatment? A propensity score matched analysis

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Author Contribution

We hereby certify that all listed co-authors were integrally involved in the formation of this manuscript via study conception/design and/or data acquisition and analysis/interpretation. Furthermore, all authors made significant contributions to the drafting or critical revisions of the manuscript, and all authors gave final approval prior to submission for publication.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

They study was approved by our local Ethical Board, register number 3675, on the 7th of March 2019. No grants or other forms of funding or assistance were utilized in the formation of this manuscript.

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Liver resection in elderly patients with extensive CRLM: are we offering **an adequate** treatment? A propensity score matched analysis

Background:

Data on the management of elderly patients with extensive colorectal liver metastases (CRLM) are scarce and conflicting. This study assesses differences in management and long-term oncological outcomes between older and younger patients with CRLM and a high Tumour Burden Score (TBS).

Methods:

International multicentre retrospective study on patients with CRLM and a category 3 TBS, submitted to liver resection. Patients were divided into two groups according to their age (younger and older than 75) and were compared using propensity score matching (PSM) analysis and multivariable regression models. Differences in management and oncological outcomes including recurrence-free survival (RFS) and overall survival (OS) were assessed

Results:

The study included 386 patients, median follow-up was 48 months. The unmatched comparison revealed a higher ASA score ($p=0.035$), less synchronous CRLM (47% vs 68%, $p=0.003$), a lower median number of lesions (1 vs 3, $p=0.004$) and less perioperative chemotherapy (CTx) (66% vs 88%, $p<0.001$) in the elderly group.

Despite the absence of CTx being an independent predictor of decreased RFS and OS (HR 0.760, $p=0.044$ and HR 0.719, $p=0.049$, respectively), the elderly group still received less CTx (OR 0.317, $p=0.001$) than the younger group.

After PSM ($n=100$ patients), the two groups were comparable, however, CTx administration was still significantly lower in the elderly group.

Conclusion: Liver resection should be considered in patients aged 75 and older, even if they present with extensive liver disease. Despite CTx being associated with improved oncological outcomes, a large percentage of elderly patients with CRLM are undertreated.

INTRODUCTION

1 During the last century, population ageing has resulted primarily from an increased life expectancy
2 due to medical advances and changes in health-related behaviour. Nearly 6% of the European
3 population was older than 80 years in 2019, and by 2050 the number of people in the European Union
4 aged 75–84 years is estimated to have increased by 56% (1).
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10 Meanwhile, the incidence of age-related diseases, such as cancer, has increased. Among them,
11 colorectal cancer (CRC) remains one of the most common cancer diagnoses, and approximately half
12 of CRC patients will develop metastases to the liver, for which surgery is the only potentially curative
13 treatment option.
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18 Advances in hepatic surgery techniques, chemotherapy and perioperative care have enabled a greater
19 proportion of elderly patients to undergo liver surgery for colorectal liver metastases (CRLM) over the
20 recent years (from 6% in 1990 to 35% in 2015) (2). However, ageing causes various physiological
21 changes, such as immune response suppression, metabolic disorders and decreased physiological
22 reserve, which are associated with an increased risk of postoperative complications after major
23 abdominal surgery (3).
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30 To date, several reports regarding the management and outcomes of elderly patients with CRLM are
31 conflicting. Some authors suggest that perioperative complications and oncological outcomes are
32 similar between younger and older patients after liver resection (4-6). Others indicate that there is an
33 increased risk of early morbidity and mortality but comparable disease recurrence rates and disease-
34 specific survival, therefore justifying the increased risk of postoperative morbidity (7-9). Additionally,
35 oncologists seem to be more restrictive in the use of perioperative chemotherapy in elderly patients,
36 although published data are confusing (10). Numerous risk scores (11-13) have been proposed to
37 estimate the prognosis of patients with CRLM, facilitate comparison among different populations and
38 improve patient stratification. The Tumor Burden Score (TBS) (13) is one of the most used scores to
39 predict recurrence of CRLM after liver resection, dividing patients in 3 categories according to the
40 extension of the liver disease. However, studies analysing outcomes in elderly patients according to
41 TBS are lacking. Furthermore, information is scarce on the management of those elderly patients at
42 high risk of disease recurrence, based on their TBS.
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55 This study aimed to evaluate the management of and oncological outcomes in elderly patients (≥ 75
56 years) diagnosed with CRLM and at high risk of disease recurrence according to their TBS (category 3).
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MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Study design

This international, multicentre, retrospective observational study was carried out in accordance with a previously published protocol (14) and recommendations arising from the Strengthening the Reporting of Observational studies in Epidemiology (STROBE) initiative (15). An invitation to collaborate with the study was initially sent to specialist liver surgery units via the Spanish Association of Surgery (Asociación Española de Cirujanos, [AEC]), and was subsequently extended to other international liver surgery units. Inclusion criteria for recruited patients were: (a) subjects older than 18 years with resectable colorectal liver metastases of histologically confirmed primary colorectal carcinoma; (b) liver resection performed in specialist liver surgery units between January 2010 and December 2015; and (c) patients with advanced CRLM – defined as those patients with a category 3 TBS (the most severe one). Patients with macroscopically affected resection margins (R2 resections) were excluded from the study.

Management

Specialised regional/local multidisciplinary teams assessed all included patients. Resectability and treatment strategy were defined according to each centre's protocol and the current international guidelines (16-19). As stated in the previously published protocol (14), the preoperative evaluation included computed tomography (CT), complemented with magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and a positron emission tomography (PET) scan in patients with suspected extrahepatic disease. Resectability was defined as the possibility of achieving complete macroscopic resection of the CRLM with an adequate future liver remnant (at least 25–30% of the preoperative liver volume). Patients with borderline resectable liver disease were submitted to a staged procedure, and those presenting with extrahepatic disease were included only if this was considered fully resectable (20-22). The hepatic transection method and Pringle manoeuvre were liberally used by each centre, according to their own protocol. Blood tests and CT were performed every three to six months for the first two years and then every six months for the first five years during follow-up (16). Recurrence was defined as documented new colorectal metastatic disease, either radiologically or by biopsy.

The study's database included patients' baseline characteristics, data on colorectal cancer resection, laboratory and radiological findings, operative details, and prognostic data, such as TBS (13). Postoperative variables included complications within the first 90 postoperative days, according to the Clavien-Dindo classification (23), histopathological analysis and oncological outcome, including

1 recurrence rate, recurrence-free survival (RFS) and overall survival (OS), calculated after excluding
2 perioperative deaths.

3 Included patients were divided into two groups according to age (patients aged 75 and over with
4 younger patients). **The reason for choosing the >75 years old cut-off was based on previous
5 publications showing the results of CRLM resection in the U.S. population (29). Furthermore, 75
6 years of age represents the middle point between “older people” (>65 years old) and “very old
7 people” (>85 years of age) following the definition of the Statistical Office of the European Union
8 (1).**

15 *Statistical analysis*

17 Descriptive data were expressed as counts and proportions for categorical variables. Continuous
18 variables were presented as means with standard deviation (SD) if normally distributed, while non-
19 normally distributed data were presented as medians with interquartile range (IQR). Univariable
20 comparisons were performed using Pearson’s χ^2 test, the Wilcoxon signed-rank test, and Cox
21 regression, for categorical, continuous and time-to-event variables respectively. Unadjusted Cox and
22 logistic regression analysis were used to identify predictors of decreases in RFS, OS and perioperative
23 chemotherapy (CTx). Variables with a $p < 0.1$ on the unadjusted analysis were subsequently included
24 in a multivariable Cox and logistic regression model. Median follow-up was calculated using the
25 reverse Kaplan Mayer method.

26 Propensity score matching (PSM) was performed to minimise confounding between groups. Prior to
27 propensity score analysis, missing data were multiply imputed ($M = 50$) using multivariable chained
28 equations (24) with the following specifications: an ordinal logistic model for ordered factor variables
29 (e.g. grade of differentiation); a Poisson regression model for count variables (e.g. number of lesions);
30 predictive mean matching with ten k-nearest neighbours for continuous variables (e.g. size of the
31 largest lesion); and augmented logistic regression for binary variables (e.g. R0 vs R1 resection) (25-27).
32 Propensity score models were developed using logistic regression modelling after multiple
33 imputation, and several models were developed and compared based on discrimination and
34 calibration. The final model consisted of the following covariates: gender, ASA score, tumour (T) status
35 and node (N) status of colorectal cancer, disease-free interval from the colorectal resection to the liver
36 resection, number and size of CRLM, KRAS and BRAF mutational status. PSM was performed using a
37 1:1 greedy matching algorithm without replacement and a caliper of $0.25 \times$ standard deviations of the
38 linear predictor. Comparisons in the matched cohort considered stratification by matched pairs;
39 hence, McNemar’s χ^2 test, the Wilcoxon signed-rank test and random effects gamma frailty Cox
40 models were used for categorical, continuous and time-to-event variables respectively.

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Statistical analyses were performed in Stata version 16.0 (StataCorp) (28), and nominal two-sided $p < 0.05$ were considered to indicate statistical significance.

RESULTS:

Assessment of baseline characteristics, surgical and oncological outcomes

A total of 386 patients, operated on between 2010 and 2015, with a category 3 TBS, were included in the study. Tables 1 and 2 present baseline and perioperative characteristics of the overall cohort, patients aged 75 years and older and the control group. As shown, 314 patients (86.1%) presented with a colorectal cancer with a T stage above two and 223 patients (60.8%) had positive lymph nodes in the surgical specimen. Additionally, 252 patients (65.4%) presented with synchronous CRLM, with bilobar lesions in 147 (58.8%) cases. A major liver resection was required in 170 cases (44.2%) and 76 (21.1%) were associated with an ablative procedure. **The high R1 resection rate (43%) found in the current series was possibly related to the selection of patients with high tumour burden. During the postoperative period, 67 patients (17.5%) presented with severe complications (\geq Clavien-Dindo IIIA), and there were 14 postoperative deaths (3.7%).**

Comparison of patients aged 75 and over with younger patients in the unmatched cohort

Patients aged 75 and older presented with more ASA III-IV cases ($p = 0.035$), less synchronous CRLM (47.2% vs 68.4%, $p = 0.003$), fewer lesions ($p = 0.005$), and received less perioperative CTx (48.4% vs 88.3%, $p < 0.001$) than younger ones. Additionally, they presented with less intraoperative blood loss (300ml vs 500ml, $p = 0.031$) (Tables 1 and 2). There were no differences in RFS (supplementary Figure S1) and OS (supplementary Figure S2).

Determinants of decreased RFS and OS in the unmatched cohort (Table 3)

The unadjusted analysis showed that advanced N colorectal cancer (HR 1.321, 95% CI 1.134–1.553, $p < 0.001$), a larger size of the biggest liver lesion (HR 1.001, 95% CI 1.000–1.003, $p = 0.014$) and the absence of perioperative chemotherapy (HR 0.753, 95% CI 0.575–0.986, $p = 0.040$) were associated with decreased RFS (Table 3). Positive lymph nodes on the colorectal surgical specimen (HR 1.213, 95% CI 1.017–1.446, $p = 0.031$), postoperative complications \geq Clavien-Dindo IIIA (HR 1.725, 95% CI 1.232–2.416, $p = 0.001$) and lack of perioperative chemotherapy (HR 0.697, 95% CI 0.508–0.957, $p = 0.026$) were associated with decreased OS.

Finally, the multivariable analysis confirmed that the absence of perioperative CTx was an independent predictor of decreased RFS and OS (HR 0.760, 95% CI 0.575–0.992, $p = 0.044$ and HR

0.719, 95% CI 0.518–0.998, $p = 0.049$ respectively). Additionally, an advanced T stage of the colorectal primary (HR 1.334, 95% CI 1.138–1.564, $p < 0.001$) was found to be an independent predictor of decreased RFS, while positive lymph nodes on the colorectal surgical specimen (HR 1.196, 95% CI 1.002–1.429, $p = 0.047$) and postoperative complications \geq Clavien-Dindo IIIA (HR 1.604, 95% CI 1.124–2.287, $p = 0.009$) were independent predictors of decreased OS.

Analysis of factors associated with perioperative chemotherapy administration (Table 4)

As the non-administration of perioperative chemotherapy was an independent predictor of decreased RFS and OS, an analysis was performed to identify factors associated with absence of perioperative CTx administration. Using the multivariable model, patients aged 75 and older received less perioperative CTx than younger ones (OR 0.317, 95% CI 0.158–0.636, $p = 0.001$), despite the presence of known recurrence risk factors. More patients with higher numbers of CRLM received CTx than those with fewer lesions (OR 1.262, 95% CI 1.089–1.461, $p = 0.002$).

Comparison of patients aged 75 and older with younger patients after PSM

The PSM model exhibited effective discrimination (Area under the curve = 0.737) and calibration ($p = 0.881$; Hosmer-Lemeshow test with ten deciles) (Supplementary Figures S3, S4). Log odds of the propensity score and baseline covariates were well balanced after matching (Table 5 and supplementary Figures S5, S6).

After PSM, the two groups were comparable in relation to all baseline characteristics, including known recurrence risk factors (Tables 5 and 6). However, patients aged 75 and older were still given less perioperative CTx (64% vs 81.6%, $p = 0.049$). No significant differences were observed between the matched groups in RFS (16 vs 15.7 months) and OS (45 vs 45 months) (Fig. 1).

DISCUSSION

The proportion of elderly patients who undergo hepatic resection for the treatment of CRLM has increased almost six times since the last decade of the 20th century. It currently includes more than one third of CRLM patients and is still rising (2). Despite representing such a large percentage of patients, elderly patients are often undertreated, and dedicated management protocols are lacking (5, 6, 16). Studies which take into consideration the subgroup of elderly patients stratified by the risk of disease recurrence are scarce. The current study is, to our knowledge, the first to describe the actual multidisciplinary management of those elderly patients with an increased risk of recurrence due to a high TBS.

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In this multicentric cohort, including ten hospitals, older patients received less perioperative chemotherapy than younger ones, all recurrence risk factors being equalised by PSM. This finding is very important because, on multivariable analysis, perioperative chemotherapy administration was the only protective factor against early recurrence and decreased overall survival in this series of selected patients with a high TBS. Based on the current study, it appears that a large percentage of CRLM patients who could benefit from systemic therapy remain undertreated. These findings are in line with previous publications (3, 6, 29) and highlight the need for protocols and objective evaluation tools that can help medical and surgical oncologists in their decision-making process with elderly patients.

Despite the difference in systemic treatment administration, elderly patients presented with similar RFS and OS to younger ones, confirming previous publications that have justified CRLM resection in this subgroup of patients (3, 5, 30). Prospective randomized trials, in our opinion, may be necessary to demonstrate the true benefit of chemotherapy administration in elderly patients. However, it is improbable that such trials will be feasible in the short term. In the absence of randomised studies, observational studies analysing the subgroup of elderly patients, such as the current, represent the best evidence to help clinicians in their decisions.

Another added value of the current study is that it suggests that liver resection is oncologically justifiable even in those elderly patients with increased tumour burden. Furthermore, no differences were found in the rate of postoperative complications and mortality between groups, in line with previous publications (4, 6, 31). Good oncological results and acceptable postoperative morbidity justify, therefore, an aggressive surgical approach. However, it is not possible to guarantee that the absence of differences in postoperative morbidity is not secondary to a type II error.

The initial comparison of the unmatched groups showed that older patients had a worse baseline status (higher ASA score) together with fewer lesions and less synchronous disease. These results are in line with previous publications (3, 29, 32) and could justify the reduced use of perioperative chemotherapy in the 75 years and older group. However, the differences in the administration of systemic therapy persisted after matching the two study groups both for baseline and oncological characteristics. In fact, in the current study, age was a risk factor for reduced administration of CTx, independent of baseline, surgical and oncological characteristics. Therefore, the decision to use less systemic therapy in the elderly group does not appear to be justified, based on either the oncological or baseline characteristics of the older patients. One possible explanation could be that older patients will not benefit from perioperative CTx in terms of overall survival, because the reduced risk of recurrence achieved by CTx is not comparable with the increased morbidity caused by systemic therapy (10). This theory is still a matter of debate in the unselected elderly CRLM population, as it is

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in younger patients, where the use of perioperative chemotherapy has not demonstrated a definitive benefit in terms of overall survival (10, 14, 33). However, in patients with elevated tumour burden, as in our series, the administration of systemic therapy has been found to achieve improved oncological outcomes (13, 16, 34), which justifies its use and the potential risk of chemotherapy-related complications. Again, the selection of patients is key in our opinion: baseline performance status and oncological features (such as TBS) should drive multidisciplinary teams in the identification of those patients who could benefit from more aggressive surgical and systemic treatment (3, 32).

The current study has several limitations that should be taken into consideration. Its retrospective nature impeded the ability to properly assess the baseline status of included patients with dedicated tools, such as the Charlson comorbidity score or frailty evaluation tools (35). The only score available to assess patients baseline status in this study was the ASA. As already mentioned, some results could be subject to type II errors and should be interpreted with caution. Furthermore, the decisions on the management of each patient were taken by local multidisciplinary teams, and the reasons to treat or not to treat a patient were not recorded for the analysis. **Included patients were all treated in specialized liver surgery units. This is not the standard of care for many patients which are treated in non-specialized hospitals. Therefore, the results of the current study could be subject to selection bias. We also acknowledge that the definition of elderly patient used in this study is somewhat arbitrary, although based on previous publications (1, 29), and the use of a different age cut-off may have led to different results.**

Despite these limitations, the current study represents a useful snapshot of real-life CRLM management in a group of international centres.

In conclusion, the present study adds to the current literature important findings on the management of a large subgroup of elderly patients with increased CRLM burden. It shows that liver resection should be considered in patient aged 75 and older, even if they present with extensive liver disease.

Furthermore, it suggests that perioperative chemotherapy administration could be a protective factor against early recurrence and decreased overall survival in TBS grade 3 patients. However, a large percentage of elderly patients with high CRLM burden, who could possibly benefit from systemic therapy, were treated differently from younger ones. These findings should be considered as the basis for further prospective studies focused on the management of such patients.

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Fig. 1: Recurrence-free survival (RFS) and Overall survival (OS) after propensity score matching.

REFERENCES

1. European Commission. Statistical Office of the European Union. Ageing Europe: looking at the lives of older people in the EU : 2020 edition. [Internet]. LU: Publications Office; 2020 [cited 2021 Feb 20]. Available from: <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2785/628105>.
2. Tufo A, Dunne DF, Manu N, Lacasia C, Jones L, de Liguori Carino N, et al. Changing outlook for colorectal liver metastasis resection in the elderly. *Eur J Surg Oncol*. 2019;45(4):635-43.
3. Booth CM, Nanji S, Wei X, Mackillop WJ. Management and Outcome of Colorectal Cancer Liver Metastases in Elderly Patients: A Population-Based Study. *JAMA Oncol*. 2015;1(8):1111-9.
4. De Blasi V, Memeo R, Adam R, Goere D, Cherqui D, Regimbeau JM, et al. Major Hepatectomy for Colorectal Liver Metastases in Patients Aged Over 80: A Propensity Score Matching Analysis. *Dig Surg*. 2018;35(4):333-41.
5. Mann CD, Neal CP, Pattenden CJ, Metcalfe MS, Garcea G, Dennison AR, et al. Major resection of hepatic colorectal liver metastases in elderly patients - an aggressive approach is justified. *Eur J Surg Oncol*. 2008;34(4):428-32.
6. Nomi T, Fuks D, Kawaguchi Y, Mal F, Nakajima Y, Gayet B. Laparoscopic major hepatectomy for colorectal liver metastases in elderly patients: a single-center, case-matched study. *Surg Endosc*. 2015;29(6):1368-75.
7. Leal JN, Sadot E, Gonen M, Lichtman S, Kingham TP, Allen PJ, et al. Operative morbidity and survival following hepatectomy for colorectal liver metastasis in octogenarians: a contemporary case matched series. *HPB (Oxford)*. 2017;19(2):162-9.
8. Nachmany I, Pencovich N, Zohar N, Goykhman Y, Lubezky N, Nakache R, et al. Resection of colorectal liver metastases in the elderly-Is it justified? *J Surg Oncol*. 2016;113(5):485-8.
9. Nardo B, Serafini S, Ruggiero M, Grande R, Fugetto F, Zullo A, et al. Liver resection for metastases from colorectal cancer in very elderly patients: New surgical horizons. *Int J Surg*. 2016;33 Suppl 1:S135-41.
10. Nassabein R, Mansour L, Richard C, Vandenbroucke-Menu F, Aubin F, Ayoub JP, et al. Outcomes of Older Patients with Resectable Colorectal Liver Metastases Cancer (CRLM): Single Center Experience. *Curr Oncol*. 2021;28(3):1899-908.
11. Fong Y, Fortner J, Sun RL, Brennan MF, Blumgart LH. Clinical score for predicting recurrence after hepatic resection for metastatic colorectal cancer: analysis of 1001 consecutive cases. *Annals of surgery*. 1999;230(3):309-18; discussion 18-21.
12. Margonis GA, Sasaki K, Gholami S, Kim Y, Andreatos N, Rezaee N, et al. Genetic And Morphological Evaluation (GAME) score for patients with colorectal liver metastases. *The British journal of surgery*. 2018;105(9):1210-20.
13. Sasaki K, Morioka D, Conci S, Margonis GA, Sawada Y, Ruzzenente A, et al. The Tumor Burden Score: A New "Metro-ticket" Prognostic Tool For Colorectal Liver Metastases Based on Tumor Size and Number of Tumors. *Annals of surgery*. 2018;267(1):132-41.
14. Di Martino M, Primavesi F, Syn N, Dorcaratto D, de la Hoz Rodriguez A, Dupre A, et al. Perioperative chemotherapy versus surgery alone for resectable colorectal liver metastases: an international multicentre propensity score matched analysis on long-term outcomes according to established prognostic risk scores. *HPB (Oxford)*. 2021.
15. von Elm E, Altman DG, Egger M, Pocock SJ, Gøtzsche PC, Vandenbroucke JP, et al. Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology (STROBE) statement: guidelines for reporting observational studies. *BMJ*. 2007;335(7624):806-8.
16. Van Cutsem E, Cervantes A, Adam R, Sobrero A, Van Krieken JH, Aderka D, et al. ESMO consensus guidelines for the management of patients with metastatic colorectal cancer. *Ann Oncol*. 2016;27(8):1386-422.
17. S3 Guideline colorectal cancer 2.1. 01/2019 ; https://www.awmf.org/uploads/tx_szleitlinien/021-007OLI_S3_Kolorektales-Karzinom-KRK_2019-01.pdf; accessed: March 31th 2021.

18. NICE guideline NG151, Jan 2020; Available at: <https://www.nice.org.uk/guidance/ng151>. Accessed March 31th, 2021
19. The National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (2020) Guideline for Clorectal Cancer (NICE guideline NG151). Available at <https://www.nice.org.uk/guidance/conditions-and-diseases/cancer/colorectal-cancer> [accessed 9 Nov 2020].
20. Qadan M, D'Angelica MI. Complex Surgical Strategies to Improve Resectability in Borderline-Resectable Disease. *Curr Colorectal Cancer Rep*. 2015;11(6):369-77.
21. Moris D, Ronnekleiv-Kelly S, Kostakis ID, Tsilimigras DI, Beal EW, Papalampros A, et al. Operative Results and Oncologic Outcomes of Associating Liver Partition and Portal Vein Ligation for Staged Hepatectomy (ALPPS) Versus Two-Stage Hepatectomy (TSH) in Patients with Unresectable Colorectal Liver Metastases: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *World J Surg*. 2018;42(3):806-15.
22. Choti MA, Thomas M, Wong SL, Eaddy M, Pawlik TM, Hirose K, et al. Surgical Resection Preferences and Perceptions among Medical Oncologists Treating Liver Metastases from Colorectal Cancer. *Ann Surg Oncol*. 2016;23(2):375-81.
23. Dindo D, Demartines N, Clavien PA. Classification of surgical complications: a new proposal with evaluation in a cohort of 6336 patients and results of a survey. *Annals of surgery*. 2004;240(2):205-13.
24. Royston P. Multiple imputation of missing values. *The Stata Journal*. 2004;4(3):227-241.
25. Wan F. Matched or unmatched analyses with propensity-score-matched data? *Statistics in medicine*. 2019;38(2):289-300.
26. Austin PC. Comparing paired vs non-paired statistical methods of analyses when making inferences about absolute risk reductions in propensity-score matched samples. *Statistics in medicine*. 2011;30(11):1292-301.
27. Linden A. A comparison of approaches for stratifying on the propensity score to reduce bias. *Journal of evaluation in clinical practice*. 2017;23(4):690-6.
28. Lunt M. Propensity Analysis in Stata Revision: 1.1. 2014. .
29. Tzeng CW, Cooper AB, Vauthey JN, Curley SA, Aloia TA. Predictors of morbidity and mortality after hepatectomy in elderly patients: analysis of 7621 NSQIP patients. *HPB (Oxford)*. 2014;16(5):459-68.
30. van Tuil T, Dhaif AA, Te Riele WW, van Ramshorst B, van Santvoort HC. Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis of Liver Resection for Colorectal Metastases in Elderly Patients. *Dig Surg*. 2019;36(2):111-23.
31. Cannon RM, Martin RC, Callender GG, McMasters KM, Scoggins CR. Safety and efficacy of hepatectomy for colorectal metastases in the elderly. *J Surg Oncol*. 2011;104(7):804-8.
32. Alabraba E, Gomez D, Nottingham HPBSG. Systematic Review of Treatments for Colorectal Metastases in Elderly Patients to Guide Surveillance Cessation Following Hepatic Resection for Colorectal Liver Metastases. *Am J Clin Oncol*. 2021;44(5):210-23.
33. Nordlinger B, Sorbye H, Glimelius B, Poston GJ, Schlag PM, Rougier P, et al. Perioperative FOLFOX4 chemotherapy and surgery versus surgery alone for resectable liver metastases from colorectal cancer (EORTC 40983): long-term results of a randomised, controlled, phase 3 trial. *The Lancet Oncology*. 2013;14(12):1208-15.
34. Yonekawa Y, Uehara K, Mizuno T, Aiba T, Ogura A, Mukai T, et al. The survival benefit of neoadjuvant chemotherapy for resectable colorectal liver metastases with high tumor burden score. *Int J Clin Oncol*. 2021;26(1):126-34.
35. Buigues C, Juarros-Folgado P, Fernandez-Garrido J, Navarro-Martinez R, Cauli O. Frailty syndrome and pre-operative risk evaluation: A systematic review. *Arch Gerontol Geriatr*. 2015;61(3):309-21.

Liver resection in elderly patients with extensive CRLM: are we offering **an adequate** treatment? A propensity score matched analysis

Background:

Data on the management of elderly patients with extensive colorectal liver metastases (CRLM) are scarce and conflicting. This study assesses differences in management and long-term oncological outcomes between older and younger patients with CRLM and a high Tumour Burden Score (TBS).

Methods:

International multicentre retrospective study on patients with CRLM and a category 3 TBS, submitted to liver resection. Patients were divided into two groups according to their age (younger and older than 75) and were compared using propensity score matching (PSM) analysis and multivariable regression models. Differences in management and oncological outcomes including recurrence-free survival (RFS) and overall survival (OS) were assessed

Results:

The study included 386 patients, median follow-up was 48 months. The unmatched comparison revealed a higher ASA score ($p=0.035$), less synchronous CRLM (47% vs 68%, $p=0.003$), a lower median number of lesions (1 vs 3, $p=0.004$) and less perioperative chemotherapy (CTx) (66% vs 88%, $p<0.001$) in the elderly group.

Despite the absence of CTx being an independent predictor of decreased RFS and OS (HR 0.760, $p=0.044$ and HR 0.719, $p=0.049$, respectively), the elderly group still received less CTx (OR 0.317, $p=0.001$) than the younger group.

After PSM ($n=100$ patients), the two groups were comparable, however, CTx administration was still significantly lower in the elderly group.

Conclusion: Liver resection should be considered in patients aged 75 and older, even if they present with extensive liver disease. Despite CTx being associated with improved oncological outcomes, a large percentage of elderly patients with CRLM are undertreated.

INTRODUCTION

During the last century, population ageing has resulted primarily from an increased life expectancy due to medical advances and changes in health-related behaviour. Nearly 6% of the European population was older than 80 years in 2019, and by 2050 the number of people in the European Union aged 75–84 years is estimated to have increased by 56% (1).

Meanwhile, the incidence of age-related diseases, such as cancer, has increased. Among them, colorectal cancer (CRC) remains one of the most common cancer diagnoses, and approximately half of CRC patients will develop metastases to the liver, for which surgery is the only potentially curative treatment option.

Advances in hepatic surgery techniques, chemotherapy and perioperative care have enabled a greater proportion of elderly patients to undergo liver surgery for colorectal liver metastases (CRLM) over the recent years (from 6% in 1990 to 35% in 2015) (2). However, ageing causes various physiological changes, such as immune response suppression, metabolic disorders and decreased physiological reserve, which are associated with an increased risk of postoperative complications after major abdominal surgery (3).

To date, several reports regarding the management and outcomes of elderly patients with CRLM are conflicting. Some authors suggest that perioperative complications and oncological outcomes are similar between younger and older patients after liver resection (4-6). Others indicate that there is an increased risk of early morbidity and mortality but comparable disease recurrence rates and disease-specific survival, therefore justifying the increased risk of postoperative morbidity (7-9). Additionally, oncologists seem to be more restrictive in the use of perioperative chemotherapy in elderly patients, although published data are confusing (10). Numerous risk scores (11-13) have been proposed to estimate the prognosis of patients with CRLM, facilitate comparison among different populations and improve patient stratification. The Tumor Burden Score (TBS) (13) is one of the most used scores to predict recurrence of CRLM after liver resection, dividing patients in 3 categories according to the extension of the liver disease. However, studies analysing outcomes in elderly patients according to TBS are lacking. Furthermore, information is scarce on the management of those elderly patients at high risk of disease recurrence, based on their TBS.

This study aimed to evaluate the management of and oncological outcomes in elderly patients (≥ 75 years) diagnosed with CRLM and at high risk of disease recurrence according to their TBS (category 3).

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Study design

This international, multicentre, retrospective observational study was carried out in accordance with a previously published protocol (14) and recommendations arising from the Strengthening the Reporting of Observational studies in Epidemiology (STROBE) initiative (15). An invitation to collaborate with the study was initially sent to specialist liver surgery units via the Spanish Association of Surgery (Asociación Española de Cirujanos, [AEC]), and was subsequently extended to other international liver surgery units. Inclusion criteria for recruited patients were: (a) subjects older than 18 years with resectable colorectal liver metastases of histologically confirmed primary colorectal carcinoma; (b) liver resection performed in specialist liver surgery units between January 2010 and December 2015; and (c) patients with advanced CRLM – defined as those patients with a category 3 TBS (the most severe one). Patients with macroscopically affected resection margins (R2 resections) were excluded from the study.

Management

Specialised regional/local multidisciplinary teams assessed all included patients. Resectability and treatment strategy were defined according to each centre's protocol and the current international guidelines (16-19). As stated in the previously published protocol (14), the preoperative evaluation included computed tomography (CT), complemented with magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and a positron emission tomography (PET) scan in patients with suspected extrahepatic disease. Resectability was defined as the possibility of achieving complete macroscopic resection of the CRLM with an adequate future liver remnant (at least 25–30% of the preoperative liver volume). Patients with borderline resectable liver disease were submitted to a staged procedure, and those presenting with extrahepatic disease were included only if this was considered fully resectable (20-22). The hepatic transection method and Pringle manoeuvre were liberally used by each centre, according to their own protocol. Blood tests and CT were performed every three to six months for the first two years and then every six months for the first five years during follow-up (16). Recurrence was defined as documented new colorectal metastatic disease, either radiologically or by biopsy.

The study's database included patients' baseline characteristics, data on colorectal cancer resection, laboratory and radiological findings, operative details, and prognostic data, such as TBS (13). Postoperative variables included complications within the first 90 postoperative days, according to the Clavien-Dindo classification (23), histopathological analysis and oncological outcome, including

recurrence rate, recurrence-free survival (RFS) and overall survival (OS), calculated after excluding perioperative deaths.

Included patients were divided into two groups according to age (patients aged 75 and over with younger patients). **The reason for choosing the >75 years old cut-off was based on previous publications showing the results of CRLM resection in the U.S. population (29). Furthermore, 75 years of age represents the middle point between “older people” (>65 years old) and “very old people” (>85 years of age) following the definition of the Statistical Office of the European Union (1).**

Statistical analysis

Descriptive data were expressed as counts and proportions for categorical variables. Continuous variables were presented as means with standard deviation (SD) if normally distributed, while non-normally distributed data were presented as medians with interquartile range (IQR). Univariable comparisons were performed using Pearson's χ^2 test, the Wilcoxon signed-rank test, and Cox regression, for categorical, continuous and time-to-event variables respectively. Unadjusted Cox and logistic regression analysis were used to identify predictors of decreases in RFS, OS and perioperative chemotherapy (CTx). Variables with a $p < 0.1$ on the unadjusted analysis were subsequently included in a multivariable Cox and logistic regression model. Median follow-up was calculated using the reverse Kaplan Mayer method.

Propensity score matching (PSM) was performed to minimise confounding between groups. Prior to propensity score analysis, missing data were multiply imputed ($M = 50$) using multivariable chained equations (24) with the following specifications: an ordinal logistic model for ordered factor variables (e.g. grade of differentiation); a Poisson regression model for count variables (e.g. number of lesions); predictive mean matching with ten k-nearest neighbours for continuous variables (e.g. size of the largest lesion); and augmented logistic regression for binary variables (e.g. R0 vs R1 resection) (25-27). Propensity score models were developed using logistic regression modelling after multiple imputation, and several models were developed and compared based on discrimination and calibration. The final model consisted of the following covariates: gender, ASA score, tumour (T) status and node (N) status of colorectal cancer, disease-free interval from the colorectal resection to the liver resection, number and size of CRLM, KRAS and BRAF mutational status. PSM was performed using a 1:1 greedy matching algorithm without replacement and a caliper of $0.25 \times$ standard deviations of the linear predictor. Comparisons in the matched cohort considered stratification by matched pairs; hence, McNemar's χ^2 test, the Wilcoxon signed-rank test and random effects gamma frailty Cox models were used for categorical, continuous and time-to-event variables respectively.

Statistical analyses were performed in Stata version 16.0 (StataCorp) (28), and nominal two-sided $p < 0.05$ were considered to indicate statistical significance.

RESULTS:

Assessment of baseline characteristics, surgical and oncological outcomes

A total of 386 patients, operated on between 2010 and 2015, with a category 3 TBS, were included in the study. Tables 1 and 2 present baseline and perioperative characteristics of the overall cohort, patients aged 75 years and older and the control group. As shown, 314 patients (86.1%) presented with a colorectal cancer with a T stage above two and 223 patients (60.8%) had positive lymph nodes in the surgical specimen. Additionally, 252 patients (65.4%) presented with synchronous CRLM, with bilobar lesions in 147 (58.8%) cases. A major liver resection was required in 170 cases (44.2%) and 76 (21.1%) were associated with an ablative procedure. **The high R1 resection rate (43%) found in the current series was possibly related to the selection of patients with high tumour burden. During the postoperative period, 67 patients (17.5%) presented with severe complications (\geq Clavien-Dindo IIIA), and there were 14 postoperative deaths (3.7%).**

Comparison of patients aged 75 and over with younger patients in the unmatched cohort

Patients aged 75 and older presented with more ASA III-IV cases ($p = 0.035$), less synchronous CRLM (47.2% vs 68.4%, $p = 0.003$), fewer lesions ($p = 0.005$), and received less perioperative CTx (48.4% vs 88.3%, $p < 0.001$) than younger ones. Additionally, they presented with less intraoperative blood loss (300ml vs 500ml, $p = 0.031$) (Tables 1 and 2). There were no differences in RFS (supplementary Figure S1) and OS (supplementary Figure S2).

Determinants of decreased RFS and OS in the unmatched cohort (Table 3)

The unadjusted analysis showed that advanced N colorectal cancer (HR 1.321, 95% CI 1.134–1.553, $p < 0.001$), a larger size of the biggest liver lesion (HR 1.001, 95% CI 1.000–1.003, $p = 0.014$) and the absence of perioperative chemotherapy (HR 0.753, 95% CI 0.575–0.986, $p = 0.040$) were associated with decreased RFS (Table 3). Positive lymph nodes on the colorectal surgical specimen (HR 1.213, 95% CI 1.017–1.446, $p = 0.031$), postoperative complications \geq Clavien-Dindo IIIA (HR 1.725, 95% CI 1.232–2.416, $p = 0.001$) and lack of perioperative chemotherapy (HR 0.697, 95% CI 0.508–0.957, $p = 0.026$) were associated with decreased OS.

Finally, the multivariable analysis confirmed that the absence of perioperative CTx was an independent predictor of decreased RFS and OS (HR 0.760, 95% CI 0.575–0.992, $p = 0.044$ and HR

0.719, 95% CI 0.518–0.998, $p = 0.049$ respectively). Additionally, an advanced T stage of the colorectal primary (HR 1.334, 95% CI 1.138–1.564, $p < 0.001$) was found to be an independent predictor of decreased RFS, while positive lymph nodes on the colorectal surgical specimen (HR 1.196, 95% CI 1.002–1.429, $p = 0.047$) and postoperative complications \geq Clavien-Dindo IIIA (HR 1.604, 95% CI 1.124–2.287, $p = 0.009$) were independent predictors of decreased OS.

Analysis of factors associated with perioperative chemotherapy administration (Table 4)

As the non-administration of perioperative chemotherapy was an independent predictor of decreased RFS and OS, an analysis was performed to identify factors associated with absence of perioperative CTx administration. Using the multivariable model, patients aged 75 and older received less perioperative CTx than younger ones (OR 0.317, 95% CI 0.158–0.636, $p = 0.001$), despite the presence of known recurrence risk factors. More patients with higher numbers of CRLM received CTx than those with fewer lesions (OR 1.262, 95% CI 1.089–1.461, $p = 0.002$).

Comparison of patients aged 75 and older with younger patients after PSM

The PSM model exhibited effective discrimination (Area under the curve = 0.737) and calibration ($p = 0.881$; Hosmer-Lemeshow test with ten deciles) (Supplementary Figures S3, S4). Log odds of the propensity score and baseline covariates were well balanced after matching (Table 5 and supplementary Figures S5, S6).

After PSM, the two groups were comparable in relation to all baseline characteristics, including known recurrence risk factors (Tables 5 and 6). However, patients aged 75 and older were still given less perioperative CTx (64% vs 81.6%, $p = 0.049$). No significant differences were observed between the matched groups in RFS (16 vs 15.7 months) and OS (45 vs 45 months) (Fig. 1).

DISCUSSION

The proportion of elderly patients who undergo hepatic resection for the treatment of CRLM has increased almost six times since the last decade of the 20th century. It currently includes more than one third of CRLM patients and is still rising (2). Despite representing such a large percentage of patients, elderly patients are often undertreated, and dedicated management protocols are lacking (5, 6, 16). Studies which take into consideration the subgroup of elderly patients stratified by the risk of disease recurrence are scarce. The current study is, to our knowledge, the first to describe the actual multidisciplinary management of those elderly patients with an increased risk of recurrence due to a high TBS.

In this multicentric cohort, including ten hospitals, older patients received less perioperative chemotherapy than younger ones, all recurrence risk factors being equalised by PSM. This finding is very important because, on multivariable analysis, perioperative chemotherapy administration was the only protective factor against early recurrence and decreased overall survival in this series of selected patients with a high TBS. Based on the current study, it appears that a large percentage of CRLM patients who could benefit from systemic therapy remain undertreated. These findings are in line with previous publications (3, 6, 29) and highlight the need for protocols and objective evaluation tools that can help medical and surgical oncologists in their decision-making process with elderly patients.

Despite the difference in systemic treatment administration, elderly patients presented with similar RFS and OS to younger ones, confirming previous publications that have justified CRLM resection in this subgroup of patients (3, 5, 30). Prospective randomized trials, in our opinion, may be necessary to demonstrate the true benefit of chemotherapy administration in elderly patients. However, it is improbable that such trials will be feasible in the short term. In the absence of randomised studies, observational studies analysing the subgroup of elderly patients, such as the current, represent the best evidence to help clinicians in their decisions.

Another added value of the current study is that it suggests that liver resection is oncologically justifiable even in those elderly patients with increased tumour burden. Furthermore, no differences were found in the rate of postoperative complications and mortality between groups, in line with previous publications (4, 6, 31). Good oncological results and acceptable postoperative morbidity justify, therefore, an aggressive surgical approach. However, it is not possible to guarantee that the absence of differences in postoperative morbidity is not secondary to a type II error.

The initial comparison of the unmatched groups showed that older patients had a worse baseline status (higher ASA score) together with fewer lesions and less synchronous disease. These results are in line with previous publications (3, 29, 32) and could justify the reduced use of perioperative chemotherapy in the 75 years and older group. However, the differences in the administration of systemic therapy persisted after matching the two study groups both for baseline and oncological characteristics. In fact, in the current study, age was a risk factor for reduced administration of CTx, independent of baseline, surgical and oncological characteristics. Therefore, the decision to use less systemic therapy in the elderly group does not appear to be justified, based on either the oncological or baseline characteristics of the older patients. One possible explanation could be that older patients will not benefit from perioperative CTx in terms of overall survival, because the reduced risk of recurrence achieved by CTx is not comparable with the increased morbidity caused by systemic therapy (10). This theory is still a matter of debate in the unselected elderly CRLM population, as it is

in younger patients, where the use of perioperative chemotherapy has not demonstrated a definitive benefit in terms of overall survival (10, 14, 33). However, in patients with elevated tumour burden, as in our series, the administration of systemic therapy has been found to achieve improved oncological outcomes (13, 16, 34), which justifies its use and the potential risk of chemotherapy-related complications. Again, the selection of patients is key in our opinion: baseline performance status and oncological features (such as TBS) should drive multidisciplinary teams in the identification of those patients who could benefit from more aggressive surgical and systemic treatment (3, 32).

The current study has several limitations that should be taken into consideration. Its retrospective nature impeded the ability to properly assess the baseline status of included patients with dedicated tools, such as the Charlson comorbidity score or frailty evaluation tools (35). The only score available to assess patients baseline status in this study was the ASA. As already mentioned, some results could be subject to type II errors and should be interpreted with caution. Furthermore, the decisions on the management of each patient were taken by local multidisciplinary teams, and the reasons to treat or not to treat a patient were not recorded for the analysis. **Included patients were all treated in specialized liver surgery units. This is not the standard of care for many patients which are treated in non-specialized hospitals. Therefore, the results of the current study could be subject to selection bias. We also acknowledge that the definition of elderly patient used in this study is somewhat arbitrary, although based on previous publications (1, 29), and the use of a different age cut-off may have led to different results.**

Despite these limitations, the current study represents a useful snapshot of real-life CRLM management in a group of international centres.

In conclusion, the present study adds to the current literature important findings on the management of a large subgroup of elderly patients with increased CRLM burden. It shows that liver resection should be considered in patient aged 75 and older, even if they present with extensive liver disease. **Furthermore, it suggests that perioperative chemotherapy administration could be a protective factor against early recurrence and decreased overall survival in TBS grade 3 patients. However, a large percentage of elderly patients with high CRLM burden, who could possibly benefit from systemic therapy, were treated differently from younger ones. These findings should be considered as the basis for further prospective studies focused on the management of such patients.**

Fig. 1: Recurrence-free survival (RFS) and Overall survival (OS) after propensity score matching.

REFERENCES

1. European Commission. Statistical Office of the European Union. Ageing Europe: looking at the lives of older people in the EU : 2020 edition. [Internet]. LU: Publications Office; 2020 [cited 2021 Feb 20]. Available from: <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2785/628105>.
2. Tufo A, Dunne DF, Manu N, Lacasia C, Jones L, de Liguori Carino N, et al. Changing outlook for colorectal liver metastasis resection in the elderly. *Eur J Surg Oncol*. 2019;45(4):635-43.
3. Booth CM, Nanji S, Wei X, Mackillop WJ. Management and Outcome of Colorectal Cancer Liver Metastases in Elderly Patients: A Population-Based Study. *JAMA Oncol*. 2015;1(8):1111-9.
4. De Blasi V, Memeo R, Adam R, Goere D, Cherqui D, Regimbeau JM, et al. Major Hepatectomy for Colorectal Liver Metastases in Patients Aged Over 80: A Propensity Score Matching Analysis. *Dig Surg*. 2018;35(4):333-41.
5. Mann CD, Neal CP, Pattenden CJ, Metcalfe MS, Garcea G, Dennison AR, et al. Major resection of hepatic colorectal liver metastases in elderly patients - an aggressive approach is justified. *Eur J Surg Oncol*. 2008;34(4):428-32.
6. Nomi T, Fuks D, Kawaguchi Y, Mal F, Nakajima Y, Gayet B. Laparoscopic major hepatectomy for colorectal liver metastases in elderly patients: a single-center, case-matched study. *Surg Endosc*. 2015;29(6):1368-75.
7. Leal JN, Sadot E, Gonen M, Lichtman S, Kingham TP, Allen PJ, et al. Operative morbidity and survival following hepatectomy for colorectal liver metastasis in octogenarians: a contemporary case matched series. *HPB (Oxford)*. 2017;19(2):162-9.
8. Nachmany I, Pencovich N, Zohar N, Goykhman Y, Lubezky N, Nakache R, et al. Resection of colorectal liver metastases in the elderly-Is it justified? *J Surg Oncol*. 2016;113(5):485-8.
9. Nardo B, Serafini S, Ruggiero M, Grande R, Fugetto F, Zullo A, et al. Liver resection for metastases from colorectal cancer in very elderly patients: New surgical horizons. *Int J Surg*. 2016;33 Suppl 1:S135-41.
10. Nassabein R, Mansour L, Richard C, Vandenbroucke-Menu F, Aubin F, Ayoub JP, et al. Outcomes of Older Patients with Resectable Colorectal Liver Metastases Cancer (CRLM): Single Center Experience. *Curr Oncol*. 2021;28(3):1899-908.
11. Fong Y, Fortner J, Sun RL, Brennan MF, Blumgart LH. Clinical score for predicting recurrence after hepatic resection for metastatic colorectal cancer: analysis of 1001 consecutive cases. *Annals of surgery*. 1999;230(3):309-18; discussion 18-21.
12. Margonis GA, Sasaki K, Gholami S, Kim Y, Andreatos N, Rezaee N, et al. Genetic And Morphological Evaluation (GAME) score for patients with colorectal liver metastases. *The British journal of surgery*. 2018;105(9):1210-20.
13. Sasaki K, Morioka D, Conci S, Margonis GA, Sawada Y, Ruzzenente A, et al. The Tumor Burden Score: A New "Metro-ticket" Prognostic Tool For Colorectal Liver Metastases Based on Tumor Size and Number of Tumors. *Annals of surgery*. 2018;267(1):132-41.
14. Di Martino M, Primavesi F, Syn N, Dorcaratto D, de la Hoz Rodriguez A, Dupre A, et al. Perioperative chemotherapy versus surgery alone for resectable colorectal liver metastases: an international multicentre propensity score matched analysis on long-term outcomes according to established prognostic risk scores. *HPB (Oxford)*. 2021.
15. von Elm E, Altman DG, Egger M, Pocock SJ, Gøtzsche PC, Vandenbroucke JP, et al. Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology (STROBE) statement: guidelines for reporting observational studies. *BMJ*. 2007;335(7624):806-8.
16. Van Cutsem E, Cervantes A, Adam R, Sobrero A, Van Krieken JH, Aderka D, et al. ESMO consensus guidelines for the management of patients with metastatic colorectal cancer. *Ann Oncol*. 2016;27(8):1386-422.
17. S3 Guideline colorectal cancer 2.1. 01/2019 ; https://www.awmf.org/uploads/tx_szleitlinien/021-007OLI_S3_Kolorektales-Karzinom-KRK_2019-01.pdf; accessed: March 31th 2021.

18. NICE guideline NG151, Jan 2020; Available at: <https://www.nice.org.uk/guidance/ng151>. Accessed March 31th, 2021
19. The National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (2020) Guideline for Clorectal Cancer (NICE guideline NG151). Available at <https://www.nice.org.uk/guidance/conditions-and-diseases/cancer/colorectal-cancer> [accessed 9 Nov 2020].
20. Qadan M, D'Angelica MI. Complex Surgical Strategies to Improve Resectability in Borderline-Resectable Disease. *Curr Colorectal Cancer Rep*. 2015;11(6):369-77.
21. Moris D, Ronnekleiv-Kelly S, Kostakis ID, Tsilimigras DI, Beal EW, Papalampros A, et al. Operative Results and Oncologic Outcomes of Associating Liver Partition and Portal Vein Ligation for Staged Hepatectomy (ALPPS) Versus Two-Stage Hepatectomy (TSH) in Patients with Unresectable Colorectal Liver Metastases: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *World J Surg*. 2018;42(3):806-15.
22. Choti MA, Thomas M, Wong SL, Eaddy M, Pawlik TM, Hirose K, et al. Surgical Resection Preferences and Perceptions among Medical Oncologists Treating Liver Metastases from Colorectal Cancer. *Ann Surg Oncol*. 2016;23(2):375-81.
23. Dindo D, Demartines N, Clavien PA. Classification of surgical complications: a new proposal with evaluation in a cohort of 6336 patients and results of a survey. *Annals of surgery*. 2004;240(2):205-13.
24. Royston P. Multiple imputation of missing values. *The Stata Journal*. 2004;4(3):227-241.
25. Wan F. Matched or unmatched analyses with propensity-score-matched data? *Statistics in medicine*. 2019;38(2):289-300.
26. Austin PC. Comparing paired vs non-paired statistical methods of analyses when making inferences about absolute risk reductions in propensity-score matched samples. *Statistics in medicine*. 2011;30(11):1292-301.
27. Linden A. A comparison of approaches for stratifying on the propensity score to reduce bias. *Journal of evaluation in clinical practice*. 2017;23(4):690-6.
28. Lunt M. Propensity Analysis in Stata Revision: 1.1. 2014. .
29. Tzeng CW, Cooper AB, Vauthey JN, Curley SA, Aloia TA. Predictors of morbidity and mortality after hepatectomy in elderly patients: analysis of 7621 NSQIP patients. *HPB (Oxford)*. 2014;16(5):459-68.
30. van Tuil T, Dhaif AA, Te Riele WW, van Ramshorst B, van Santvoort HC. Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis of Liver Resection for Colorectal Metastases in Elderly Patients. *Dig Surg*. 2019;36(2):111-23.
31. Cannon RM, Martin RC, Callender GG, McMasters KM, Scoggins CR. Safety and efficacy of hepatectomy for colorectal metastases in the elderly. *J Surg Oncol*. 2011;104(7):804-8.
32. Alabraba E, Gomez D, Nottingham HPBSG. Systematic Review of Treatments for Colorectal Metastases in Elderly Patients to Guide Surveillance Cessation Following Hepatic Resection for Colorectal Liver Metastases. *Am J Clin Oncol*. 2021;44(5):210-23.
33. Nordlinger B, Sorbye H, Glimelius B, Poston GJ, Schlag PM, Rougier P, et al. Perioperative FOLFOX4 chemotherapy and surgery versus surgery alone for resectable liver metastases from colorectal cancer (EORTC 40983): long-term results of a randomised, controlled, phase 3 trial. *The Lancet Oncology*. 2013;14(12):1208-15.
34. Yonekawa Y, Uehara K, Mizuno T, Aiba T, Ogura A, Mukai T, et al. The survival benefit of neoadjuvant chemotherapy for resectable colorectal liver metastases with high tumor burden score. *Int J Clin Oncol*. 2021;26(1):126-34.
35. Buigues C, Juarros-Folgado P, Fernandez-Garrido J, Navarro-Martinez R, Cauli O. Frailty syndrome and pre-operative risk evaluation: A systematic review. *Arch Gerontol Geriatr*. 2015;61(3):309-21.

Table 1 Comparison of baseline and preoperative characteristics in patients ≥ 75 years old and younger

	All patients (n=386)			
	Total (n=386)	$\geq 75y$ (n=53)	$< 75y$ (n=333)	p value
<i>Patient characteristics</i>				
Male gender, n/total (%)*	248/386 (64.2%)	32/53 (60.4%)	216/333 (64.9%)	0.527
ASA classification, n/total (%)*				
ASA I-II	249/373 (66.8%)	26/51 (50.9%)	223/322 (69.2%)	0.035
ASA III-IV	124/373 (33.2%)	25/51 (49.1%)	99/322 (30.7%)	
<i>Disease characteristics</i>				
Cirrhosis, n/total (%)*	1/328 (0.6%)	0/41 (0%)	2/287 (0.7%)	0.592
T stage 3 or 4, n/total (%)*	314/365 (86.1%)	43/51 (84.3%)	271/314 (86.3%)	0.109
N stage 1 or 2, n/total (%)*	223/367 (60.8%)	28/52 (53.8%)	195/315 (61.9%)	0.251
Synchronous CRLM, n/total (%)*	252/385 (65.4%)	25/53 (47.2%)	227/332 (68.4%)	0.003
Total bilirubin, mg/dL, mean (IQR)	0.7 (0.5 to 0.9)	0.7 (0.6 to 1)	0.7 (0.4 to 0.9)	0.188
Albumin, mg/dL, median (IQR)	4.1 (4.0 to 4.3)	4.1 (4.0 to 4.5)	4.1 (3.9 to 4.3)	0.551
CEA, median (IQR)	9.4 (3.5 to 37.9)	9.8 (2.9 to 28.1)	8.8 (3.5 to 39.3)	0.962
Number of CRLM, median (IQR)*	3 (2 to 5)	3 (2 to 4)	3 (2 to 6)	0.005
Size of largest CRLM, mm, median (IQR)	40 (30 to 65)	42 (30 to 65)	40 (30 to 62)	0.534
Location of CRLM, n/total (%)*				
Unilobar	103/250 (41.2%)	17/33 (51.6%)	86/217 (39.6%)	0.196
Bilobar	147/250 (58.8%)	16/33 (48.4%)	131/217 (60.3%)	
<i>Perioperative Chemotherapy</i>				
Perioperative Chemotherapy, n (%)	329/386 (85.2%)	35/53 (66.0%)	294/333 (88.3%)	<0.001
*Denominators may differ from total sample size due to missing data				
† Denominator only includes patients who received neoadjuvant systemic therapy				
NA: not applicable, CRLM: Colorectal liver metastases, ASA: American society of anaesthesiologists, CEA: carcinoembryonic antigen				

Table 2 Comparison of surgical characteristics and post-operative outcomes in patients ≥ 75 years old and younger

	All patients (n=386)			
	Total (n=386)	$\geq 75y$ (n=53)	<75y (n=333)	p value
<i>Surgical and perioperative data</i>				
Major resection, n/total (%)*	170/385 (44.2%)	23/53 (43.4%)	147/332 (44.3%)	0.905
Associated ablative procedures, n/total (%)*	76/360 (21.1%)	9/49 (18.4%)	67/311 (21.5%)	0.613
Pringle maneuver time, median (IQR) [†]	26 (7.5 to 40.5)	22 (0 to 31)	27 (9 to 42)	0.119
Blood loss (ml), median (IQR)	500 (200 to 944)	300 (196 to 500)	500 (240 to 1000)	0.031
Laparoscopic procedures, n/total (%)*	12/354 (3.4%)	3/46 (6.5%)	9/308 (2.9%)	0.208
Two-stage procedures n/total (%)*	34/247 (13.8%)	2/33 (6.1%)	32/214 (14.9%)	0.168
<i>Post-operative complications</i>				
Complications \geq Clavien-Dindo IIIA, n/total (%)*	67/382 (17.5%)	7/53 (13.21%)	60/329 (18.2%)	0.372
Bile leakage, n/total (%)*	31/374 (8.3%)	1/50 (2.0%)	30/324 (9.3%)	0.083
Hemorrhage, n/total (%)*	9/371 (2.4%)	2/50 (4.0%)	7/321 (2.2%)	0.437
Post-operative liver failure n/total (%)*	10/372 (2.7%)	1/50 (2.0%)	9/322 (2.8%)	0.746
Intrabdominal infection, n/total (%)*	49/381 (12.9%)	4/52 (7.7%)	45/329 (13.7%)	0.231
Reoperation, n/total (%)*	19/380 (5.0%)	1/53 (1.9%)	18/327 (5.5%)	0.262
90-days mortality n/total (%)*	14/383 (3.7%)	2/53 (3.8%)	12/330 (3.6%)	0.961
LOS ITU, days, median (IQR)	1 (0 to 5)	1 (0 to 2)	1 (0 to 5)	0.512
LOS, days, median (IQR)	7 (5 to 10)	7 (6 to 12)	7 (5 to 10)	0.336
<i>Histopathological findings</i>				
R0, n (%)	210/370 (56.8%)	23/50 (46.0%)	187/320 (58.4%)	0.124
Grade, n/total (%)				
Well/moderately-differentiated	367/386 (95.1%)	51/53 (96.2%)	316/333 (94.9%)	0.677
Poorly/un-differentiated	19/386 (4.9%)	2/53 (3.8%)	17/333 (5.1%)	
K-RAS/B-RAS positive, n/total (%)*	31/136 (22.7%)	1/12 (8.3%)	30/124 (24.1%)	0.211

*Denominators may differ from total sample size due to missing data

[†]Pringle time was calculated only for patients for whom the Pringle maneuver was used

NA: not applicable; NR: not reached; LOS: length of stay; ITU: intensive therapy unit

Table 3: Unadjusted and multivariable analysis of factors related to recurrence free survival and overall survival from the unmatched cohort.

Recurrence Free Survival						
Variable	Unadjusted analysis			Multivariable analysis		
	HR	95%CI	p-Value	HR	95%CI	p-Value
Age ≥75	.784	.544-1.129	0.192			
ASA classification	1.019	.864-1.201	0.822			
Disease-free survival from colorectal resection	.995	.986-1.004	0.350			
T stage colorectal cancer	1.141	.944-1.381	0.171			
N stage colorectal cancer	1.321	1.134-1.553	<0.001	1.334	1.138-1.564	<0.001
Number of lesions	.991	.952-1.031	0.659			
Size of the biggest lesion	1.001	1.000-1.003	0.014	-	-	-
Type of resection (major vs minor)	.958	.752-1.220	0.730			
Complications ≥ Clavien-Dindo IIIA	.773	.544-1.099	0.152			
Radicality CRLM resection (R1 vs R0)	1.010	.791-1.289	0.935			
KRAS/BRAF mutation*	1.269	.779-2.068	0.338			
Perioperative chemotherapy	.753	.575-.986	0.040	.760	.575-.992	0.044
Overall Survival						
Variable	Unadjusted analysis			Multivariable analysis		
	HR	95%CI	p-Value	HR	95%CI	p-Value
Age ≥75	.968	.654-.434	0.874			
ASA classification	1.131	.927-1.380	0.225			
Disease-free survival from colorectal resection	.991	.981-1.002	0.142			
T stage colorectal cancer	1.106	.883-1.386	0.379			
N stage colorectal cancer	1.213	1.017-1.446	0.031	1.196	1.002-1.429	0.047
Number of lesions	1.008	.965-1.052	0.710			
Size of the biggest lesion	.999	.997-1.001	0.954			
Type of resection (major vs minor)	.998	.758-1.313	0.991			
Complications ≥ Clavien-Dindo IIIA	1.725	1.232-2.416	0.001	1.604	1.124-2.287	0.009
Radicality CRLM resection (R1 vs R0)	.991	.749-1.312	0.953			
KRAS/BRAF mutation*	1.465	.853-2.516	0.166			
Perioperative chemotherapy	.697	.508-.957	0.026	.719	.518-.998	0.049

Table 4: Unadjusted and multivariable analysis of factors associated with perioperative chemotherapy administration.

Perioperative chemotherapy administration						
Variable	Unadjusted analysis			Multivariable analysis		
	OR	95%CI	p-Value	OR	95%CI	p-Value
Age ≥75	.257	.133-.498	<0.001	.317	.158-.636	0.001
Gender	.730	.396-1.344	0.313			
ASA classification	1.027	.558-1.890	0.930			
Diabetes	.698	.300-1.621	0.404			
Chronic liver disease	.294	.0480-1.805	0.186			
Number of lesions	1.268	1.098-1.466	0.001	1.262	1.089-1.461	0.002
Size of the biggest lesion	.998	.995-1.002	0.509			
Unilobar vs bilobar CRLM	1.147	.300-4.380	0.840			
Type of resection (major vs minor)	1.558	.867-2.800	0.137			
Complications ≥ Clavien-Dindo IIIA	2.451	.940-6.393	0.067			
Intrabdominal infection	2.978	.893-9.925	0.076			
Postoperative bleeding	1.311	.160-10.711	0.800			
Biliary leak	1.630	.477-5.561	0.435			
Postoperative liver failure	1.509	.187-12.166	0.699			

Table 5 Comparison of baseline and preoperative characteristics in patients ≥ 75 years old and younger after PSM analysis

	Propensity-score matched cohort (n=100)		
	$\geq 75y$ (n=50)	$< 75y$ (n=50)	<i>p</i> value
<i>Patient characteristics</i>			
Male gender, n/total (%)*	30/50 (65%)	35/50 (70%)	0.398
ASA classification, n/total (%)*			
ASA I-II	26/48 (54.2%)	18/48 (37.5%)	0.267
ASA III-IV	22/48 (45.8%)	30/48 (62.5%)	
<i>Disease characteristics</i>			
Cirrhosis n/total (%)*	0/39 (0%)	1/44 (1.1%)	0.658
T stage 3 or 4, n/total (%)*	40/48 (83.3%)	33/46 (71.7%)	0.275
N stage 1 or 2, n/total (%)*	26/49 (53.1%)	20/46 (43.5%)	0.668
Synchronous CRLM, n/total (%)*	24/50 (48%)	18/50 (36%)	0.430
Total bilirubin, mg/dL, mean (SD)	0.7 (0.5 to 1)	0.7 (0.5 to 0.9)	0.757
Albumin, mg/dL, median (IQR)	4.1 (4 to 4.5)	4.1 (3.9 to 4.3)	0.690
CEA, median (IQR)	10 (3 to 29.4)	8.5 (2.5 to 55)	0.874
Number of CRLM, median (IQR)	3 (2 to 4)	3 (2 to 4)	0.454
Size of bigger CRLM, median (IQR)	41 (30 to 70)	45 (31 to 65)	0.858
Location of CRLM, n/total (%)*			
Unilobar	14/29 (48.2%)	17/32 (53.1%)	1.000
Bilobar	15/29 (51.7%)	15/32 (46.8%)	
<i>Perioperative Chemotherapy</i>			
Perioperative Chemotherapy, n (%)	29/50 (58%)	40/50 (81.6%)	0.048
*Denominators may differ from total sample size due to missing data			
† Denominator only includes patients who received neoadjuvant systemic therapy			
NA: not applicable; CRLM: Colorectal liver metastases, ASA: American society of anaesthesiologists, CEA: carcinoembryonic antigen			

Table 6 Comparison of surgical characteristics and post-operative outcomes in patients ≥ 75 years old and younger after PSM analysis

	Propensity-score matched cohort (n=100)		
	$\geq 75y$ (n=50)	$<75y$ (n=50)	p value
<i>Surgical and perioperative data</i>			
Major resection, n/total (%)*	21/50 (42%)	24/50 (48%)	0.658
Associated ablative procedures, n/total (%)*	8/46 (17.4%)	6/49 (12.2%)	0.578
Pringle maneuver time, median (IQR) [†]	23.5 (0 to 36)	25 (8 to 43)	0.402
Blood loss (ml), median (IQR)	400 (196 to 550)	500 (200 to 600)	0.694
Laparoscopic resection n/total (%)*	2/43 (4.6%)	2/47 (4.3%)	0.666
Two-stage procedures n/total (%)*	2/32 (4.8%)	1/30 (3.3%)	0.896
<i>Post-operative complications</i>			
Complications \geq Clavien-Dindo IIIA, n/total (%)*	7/50 (12%)	10/49 (20.4%)	0.658
Bile leakage, n/total (%)*	2/48 (4.1%)	4/46 (8.7%)	0.669
Hemorrhage, n/total (%)*	2/48 (4.2%)	3/48 (6.2%)	0.916
Post-operative liver failure n/total (%)*	1/48 (2.1%)	2/47 (4.2%)	0.834
Intrabdominal infection, n/total (%)*	4/49 (8.2%)	6/49 (12.2%)	0.831
Reoperation, n/total (%)*	1/50 (2%)	5/49 (10.2%)	0.604
90-days mortality n/total (%)*	2/50 (4%)	1/49 (2%)	1.000
LOS ITU, days, median (IQR)	1 (0 to 1.5)	1 (1 to 4.5)	0.226
LOS, days, median (IQR)	7 (6 to 12)	6 (5 to 9)	0.052
<i>Histopathological findings</i>			
R0, n (%)	22/47 (44%)	25/50 (50%)	1.000
Grade, n/total (%)			
Well/moderately-differentiated	48/50 (96%)	48/50 (96%)	1.000
Poorly/un-differentiated	2/50 (4%)	2/50 (4%)	
K-RAS/B-RAS positive, n/total (%)*	1/12 (8.3%)	4/17 (23.5%)	0.841
<i>Oncological outcomes</i>			
Follow-up (months), median	39.6	38.6	0.709
Recurrence-free survival (months)			
Median (IQR)	15.8 (8 to NR)	14.5 (4.4 to 48)	
1-year RFS (%)	64.8%	53.1%	0.325
3-year RFS (%)	36.5%	30.8%	
5-year RFS (%)	30.9%	23.1%	
Overall survival (months)			
Median (IQR)	48 (28 to 82.8)	45 (20.3 to NR)	
1-year OS (%)	93.1%	87.8%	0.984
3-year OS (%)	64.5%	59.9%	
5-year OS (%)	40.1%	44.6%	

*Denominators may differ from total sample size due to missing data

[†]Pringle time was calculated only for patients for whom the Pringle maneuver was used

[‡] NA: not applicable; NR: not reached; LOS: length of stay; ITU: intensive therapy unit; RFS: recurrence-free survival, OS: overall survival

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Conflicts of Interest Statement

Manuscript title: _____

Liver resection in elderly patients with extensive CRLM: are we offering the right treatment?

A propensity score matched analysis

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We hereby certify that all listed co-authors were integrally involved in the formation of this manuscript via study conception/design and/or data acquisition and analysis/interpretation. Furthermore, all authors made significant contributions to the drafting or critical revisions of the manuscript, and all authors gave final approval prior to submission for publication.